

Real Life Applications in Graph Theory

Application of Graph Theory in Google Maps

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Abstract

This paper focuses on finding the shortest path in Google maps using Dijkstra's algorithm. Generally, a path is nothing but a sequence of vertices each adjacent to the next. The main objective in this paper is to achieve the method of running Google map services by using graph theory to compute the shortest path and its implementation using the Dijkstra's algorithm in graph theory. The diagram illustrates certain shortest path findings in this paper

Keywords: *Edges, Vertices, Shortest Path, Dijkstra's Algorithm, Google Maps, Nodes*

Vertices

Here, the vertices are represented as points (or) nodes (or) junctions. It is denoted by $V = \{v_{(1,)}, v_{(2,)}, \dots, v_{(n)}\}$.

Edges

The line segments joining the two vertices are called edges. It is denoted by $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$.

Path

The roads connecting these points are called path. A path is a walk through sequence of vertices $V = \{v_{(1,)}, v_{(2,)}, \dots, v_{(n)}\}$, each adjacent to next, without any repetition of vertices.

Example: The diagram clearly shows that there are many paths in these two graphs.

Now consider in graph H, one of the Path = $\{v_{(1,)}, v_{(2,)}, v_{(3,)}, v_{(4)}\}$.

Weight of Graph

A graph in which weights are assigned to every edge is called weighted graph.

Example: Distances, time, traffic conditions (or) road types.

To find the shortest path between the starting and terminal node by using Dijkstra's algorithm. Dijkstra's algorithm is one of the greedy algorithms used to optimize and find the shortest path between nodes in a graph. This algorithm is an effective algorithm proposed by Edsger. W. Dijkstra in the year 1956 and published three years later. This algorithm is used for finding the shortest path between the vertices in a weighted graph. In graph theory, the shortest path problem is the problem of finding a path between two vertices in a graph which equals that the sum of the weights of its constituent edges is minimized.

The following are the steps for finding shortest path (Dijkstra's Algorithm)

Mark the ending vertex with a distance of zero. Designate this vertex as current.

Find all vertices leading to the current vertex. Calculate their distances to the end.

Mark the current vertex as visited.

Mark the vertex with the smallest distance as current, and repeat from step 2

Example:

Find the shortest path from vertex A to every other vertex.

Solution

Consider, the source node A of the above graph is considered as 0. The path from initial vertex A to every other vertex is shown in the table given below:

Vertices	Weights	Path
A,B	$0+4=4$	A-B
A,C	$0+2=2$	A-C
A,B,C	$0+4+5=9$	A-B-C
A,B,D	$0+4+10=14$	A-B-D
A,C,E,D	$0+2+3+4=9$	A-C-E-D
A,C,E	$0+2+3=5$	A-C-E
A,B,C,E	$0+4+5+3=12$	A-B-C-E
A,B,D,F	$0+4+10+11=25$	A-B-D-F
A,C,E,D,F	$0+2+3+4+11=20$	A-C-E-D-F

Finding the Shortest Path

Therefore, there are two paths from source node A to destination node F. The number of weights in one path A-B-D-F is 25 and in another path A-C-E-D-F is 20. Hence, by Dijkstra's algorithm, the shortest path is considered as the one with the minimum weight assigned to it. Therefore, the shortest path from the initial vertex A to final vertex F is A-C-E-D-F. Since the weights calculated in this path sum to 20 (minimum) and the other path sum to 25. Therefore the shortest path is A-C-E-D-F. In the above graph, the shortest path is indicated by the blue lines.

Navigation Calculation in Google Maps

The search for direction on Google maps is possible. Its system uses Dijkstra's algorithm to find the shortest path through the network of roads (roads) connecting the starting point and destination. i.e., the number of vehicles on the road is calculated and the traffic, road congestion also are calculated for time consumption to travel from one node to another node. Thus, the minimum number of vehicles on the road is calculated as the minimum number of weights on the edges whatever the distance may be, it is considered as the shortest path or shortest route in Google maps.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the graph theory, particularly Dijkstra's algorithm, plays a vital role in finding the shortest and most efficient paths in real-world applications like Google maps. By calculating the minimum weights i.e. In terms of distance, time, or traffic, road congestion, the Dijkstra's algorithm helps to optimize navigation and improve travel efficiency. The ability to determine the shortest path accurately shows the significance of mathematical concepts in solving everyday problems.

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